

The Last White Hunter: Reminiscences of the Bygone Era of Shikar Literature

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Abstract

Sketching the biography of a hunter in an era when hunting wild animals has been banned is a bold venture to reminisce the bygone era of hunting the wild animals. *Shikar* or hunting has been a recreational sport during the days of *Raj* in India. Both the Indian rulers and the British administrators practiced *shikar*. Names like Jim Corbett and Kenneth Anderson are well known as they were not just hunters, but also writers who recorded their hunting adventures. However, after the end of colonialism and the rise of environmentalism, hunting came to be on the decline and banned totally by 1972. Donald Anderson, both literally and metaphorically, was the last white hunter on the Indian soil as his chronicler Joshua Matthew puts it in the biography *The Last white Hunter: Reminiscences of a Colonial Shikari*. An attempt has been made here to study this book.

Keywords

Hunting, shikar literature, Donald Anderson, Environmentalism, Conservation.

Introduction

The Last white Hunter: Reminiscences of a Colonial Shikari (2018) by Joshua Matthews is a biographical account of Donald Anderson, the son of the famous hunter Kenneth Anderson. Arguably the last of the shikaris from India's colonial past, Donald Anderson did not write about his hunting adventures like his father Kenneth Anderson or Jim Corbett both of whom were great hunters and writers of shikar literature. Donald had a dubious and carefree life which varied from hunting tigers and panthers and angling for the mahseer, to being a stunt double in a Hollywood film, and eventually living his last days in penury in Bengaluruⁱ.

Objective of study

An attempt has been made here to study book *The Last white Hunter: Reminiscences of a Colonial Shikari*.

Review of Literature

Theodore Bhaskaran emphasises that Shikar literature has some characteristics that popularise the genre: "It is always in the first person. It is typically about a man following a dangerous animal and destroying it in its habitat. These components are the ingredients of a thriller! Another reason for the genre's attractiveness is that its stories are believed to be factual"ⁱⁱ. Bhaskaran adds that the book is bound to be valuable for anyone in love with the Indian wilderness.

No Beast So Fierce: The Champavat Tiger and Her Hunter, The First Tiger Conservationist by Dane Hucklebridge provides a critical overview of Jim Corbett's evolution as a Hunter-Conservationist and his account of killing the man-eating tiger of Champavat. Hucklebridge attributes the role of poachers in creating man eaters. A poacher "does not see the tiger as a divine spirit, a lord of the forest, a custodian of the natural world, maintaining the balance of all things. To him, a tiger is a sack of gold and nothing more: money for clearing land, funds to buy a buffalo and start a farm of the own" (p.9). This brings out material interest as one of the important factors behind the destruction of flora and fauna in Indian jungles.

Sporting Days in Southern India by A.J.O Pollock (1894) in another early shikar writing from the Indian subcontinent. Like other colonial masters, Pollock too thinks of the big game hunting as an activity of pleasure seeking. On one occasion, he admits to having shot a panthress along with three unborn cubs in the stomach. "A post-mortem revealed three unborn cubs, about the size of rats, which although devoid of hair, bare the marks of all the rosettes very clearly" (p.54). While the native Indians regarded the felines in the Indian Jungle with respect and fear and gave them a wider berth, the colonialist in India saw tigers, leopards and panthers as animals to be conquered and destroyed.

Jack Denton Scott, an American Journalist recounts shooting adventures in Indian jungles in his book *Forests of the Nights*. His accounts reveal a transformed mindset among hunters: "careless or too quick shooting can wound tiger or a leopard, and it can prey on these unarmed villagers for months after the hunter has gone back" (p.50). He does mention the attractive sums offered in the wild markets of the west-"peacocks would sell for seventy-five to one hundred and fifty dollars in America and England. Some bird collectors would as high as two hundred for an especially beautiful, well colored male with a tail. (p. 77). Not just for sportive pleasure, but for the money being offered for wild animals and animal artifacts exacerbated the extinction of wild in the exotic forests including Indian Jungles. Upon reviving invitation for from and Indian Maharaja, Scott narrates: "we walked into a room covered with a gigantic rug made of tiger skins, so many that his highness did not even know the exact figure. He had shot them all, as well as those that were head mounted on the wall, encircling us like a jungle nightmare" (p.159).

Shikar literature is not an act of self-bragging. Self-glorification is not what true Shikar writing does. Instead, shikar writings reflect the strenuous, challenging task of bagging an animal like tiger or leopard in its territory, the forest. Shikar writers like Jim Corbett and Kenneth Anderson are known for the tenacity with which they pursued notorious man-eating tigers and leopards. Armed with natural weapons like strong jaws, teeth, talons, speed, agility, brute physical strength and strong sense organs, tigers, leopards and bears have better edge over human beings. Sharp senses, skill, good weapons and a strong sense of judgment coupled with experience about jungle and its denizens make a hunter a true shikar.

Main Text

Donald Anderson: The Last White Hunter

The Last white Hunter: Reminiscences of a Colonial Shikari by Joshua Matthews is a biographical account of Donald Anderson, the son of the famous hunter Kenneth Anderson. Donald Anderson was born in 1934, and his boyhood was like any other non-Indian at that point in time in Bangalore. As Joshua Matthews puts it, Donald "was more 'Indian' than his father, and blended with the rest of the population as he grew up. He loved hunting and the forests much like his father and lived a rather colourful life, witnessing an incredible transformation in the world around him, over the 80 years he livedⁱⁱⁱ" Published in 2018, four years after the demise of Donald Anderson and many years after the death of Kenneth Anderson, the book corroborates some of the incidents mentioned in the shikar writings of Kenneth Anderson- a testimony to the authenticity of Kenneth Anderson's writings. However, Donald Anderson never resorted to writing his experiences the reason for which is expressed by himself in the following way: "Unlike my father, who was equally good with the gun and the pen, my skill has been only with the former, and hence I always dismissed the notion of putting together my memories in written form---"(p-1).

This also explains us why most of the good hunters fail to impress their readers through their shikar writings. Donald echoes the words of Kenneth Anderson when he shares his admiration for nature: "I can never understand people who say that they could not do without city life. When here, in a place akin to paradise. There are a million things that are so breathtaking to watch and observe" However, upon growing old, Don recollects a tough question to which he never had an answer: "Many people have asked me whether I regret shooting so many animals, and it is perhaps the toughest question I have been asked in my life". Not just Donald Anderson, almost all hunters do not have answer to this question. Rather, they shun such questions. However, while recollecting his shikar days, Donald sums up like this:

I will not defend my hunting some of the larger animals as some sort of service I did to protect people, but the truth of the matter is that tigers, panthers and wild dogs were treated as vermin in those days and hunters were rewarded for killing them.

It was custom during the colonial era to consider the jungle animals as vermins and hunt them. The British Government in India did not have any intentions to preserve or conserve India's forests or wild life. Therefore, it is not surprising to find out that hunters were rewarded by people and the British Government. On the other hand, until the 1980s, Indians too, at large, did not have a serious consideration for wild life conservation.

The passing of Indian wild life act in 1972 brought an unspectacular end to the hunting days of Donald. However, even after the passing of law, he observes hunting and poaching still continued:

The act was not passed overnight; there had been a lot of rumors, and many amateur shikaris went overboard with their last hunt. Suddenly, the forest department folk started to look at me with suspicion, and it was ironic that licensed gun holders like me, who always followed rules,

bore the brunt of this treatment, while poachers and others who were hand in glove with the department got away with so much more than just moving in the jungles.

Donald here is not lamenting the curtailment of his freedom as a hunter. Rather, he is trying to point out the shallow nature of laws and the difficulty in implementing them in a vast country like India. Also, these words posit a lack of awareness among the masses regarding the conservation of wildlife.

Donald also recounts that even independence did not bring much change in the attitudes of the people of India regarding hunting or poaching: "After independence, there was a significant spurt of nefarious activity in these parts. Although the British were still around, Indians started getting bolder in their quest to get richer. Locally made matchlocks and country bombs appeared on the scene and were mainly used for poaching animals". This remark clearly explains why India's wildlife declined so rapidly after 1947 up to the passing of the Indian wildlife protection act of 1972^{iv} After the demise of Donald Anderson, "the last white hunter", it has become evident that the legacy of shikar literature is becoming a thing of the past. However, with increasing instances of man-animal conflicts across the states in India and the inability of the concerned officials in the Forest Departments to bring an amicable solution to the menace, a high time has come - not just in the domain of academics, but also during the moments of forming action plans - to revisit shikar literature that will offer firsthand knowledge on many aspects related to man wildlife conflicts and wildlife behaviour.

Julie Hughes is critical about the views of Donald Anderson. She opines that "The Last White Hunter presents a familiar explanation for post-colonial environmental change—shikar is not to blame for environmental devastation and the loss of wildlife. Rather, these sportsmen had maintained ecosystem balance by culling excess stock and eliminating specific rogue animals, and in the early days these "penitent butchers" were the only ones sufficiently invested and knowledgeable to successfully develop and enforce conservationism". Further, she adds that "Anderson's sporting code fails as anything beyond a niche environmentalist ethic with severely limited participation. What we desperately need now are broadly replicable ways of living—and living comfortably—that stop further damage to (and hopefully begin to restore) the things we most love and need" ^v.

Conclusion

The Last White Hunter places our perspectives towards the direction of transition that has come over hunters in India. Also, it points out the fact that there were elements of nobility, courage and perseverance which are involved in the act of hunting carnivorous animals. The text manages to convey the voices for conservation and the attempts aimed at protection of wildlife in India without blending any sense of disappointment over the loss of opportunity to hunt. It is true that hunting was very popular when there were plenty of wild animals. As they got reduced, the practitioners of wildlife hunting came to be in a precarious position- whether to support conservation or to drift away silently. While hunters like Kenneth Anderson and Jim Corbett turned themselves into conservation, Donald Anderson remained aloof and drew himself into seclusion. As the title itself sums it all, he was the last white hunter in India.

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